

Setting DOI OJS V.2 dan OJS 3

Sharing Session Bersama Supervisor RJI #8

Rabu, 2 Juli 2025

13.00 WIB s.d. selesai

Zoom Meeting

SALAM!

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- A digital object identifier (DOI) is a *unique* alphanumeric string assigned by a registration agency (the International DOI Foundation) to identify content and provide a persistent link to its location on the internet. The publisher assigns a DOI when your article is published and made available electronically.
- ▶ Sumber: [What is a digital object identifier, or DOI? \(6th edition\) \(apa.org\)](#)

Beberapa Lembaga Penyedia DOI

[Airiti, Inc.](#)

[Crossref](#)

[JaLC \(Japan Link Center\)](#)

[Korea Institute of Science and Technology Information \(KISTI\)](#)

[China National Knowledge Infrastructure \(CNKI\)](#)

[DataCite](#)

[mEDRA \(Multilingual European DOI Registration Agency\)](#)

[OP \(Publications Office of the European Union\)](#)

[EIDR \(Entertainment Identifier Registry\)](#)

[ISTIC & Wanfang Data \(The Institute of Scientific and Technical Information of China & Wanfang Data Co., Ltd.\)](#)

Sumber: https://doi.org/registration_agencies.html

Mengapa Perlu DOI

Syarat wajib akreditasi jurnal ilmiah online

Salah Satu Point Penilaian Di ARJUNA

Memberikan tautan baku pada Artikel

http://doi.org/ 10.4225 / 01/4F3DB08617645

resolver service prefix
(assigning body) suffix
(resource)

Figure 1: Anatomy of a DOI

Sumber: [anatomy-of-a-doi.jpg \(720×203\) \(ands.org.au\)](#)

Beberapa contoh pola sebuah DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.33360/joall.v6i2.15369>

<https://doi.org/10.1017/S0272263121000322>

Persiapan Setting DOI 1/2

1. Periksa nama jurnal pada <https://issn.brin.go.id> dan <https://portal.issn.org>
2. Periksa setup 1-5 pada OJS.
3. Periksa seluruh *metadata* penulis pada OJS khususnya bagian *first name, middle name, last name*. Jika hanya 1 suku kata maka ulangi nama tsb pada *last name*.
4. Periksa nama penulis (**wajib** tanpa gelar seperti Prof., Dr., Mr., Rr).

Persiapan Setting DOI 2/2

5. Periksa ORCID ID penulis (**sebaiknya ada**).
6. Periksa metadata judul artikel (judul, abstrak, bahasa, *references*).
7. Periksa *full text* pada Galley dan pastikan sudah terunggah dalam bentuk **pdf**.
8. Periksa metadata *copyright* (nama penulis, tahun terbit, dan lisensi yg digunakan).
9. **Periksa kembali** seluruh *metadata* artikel sebelum aktivasi DOI. Jika ada hasil revisi maka *metadata* harus diperbaharui sebelum penerbitan.

Setting DOI (ojs V.2)

Home > User > Journal Management > Plugin Management > **Public Identifier Plugins**

Public Identifier Plugins

These plugins implement support for a public identifier.

- **DOI**

This plugin enables the assignment of the Digital Object Identifiers to issues, articles, galleys and supplementary files in OJS.

[DISABLE](#) [SETTINGS](#) [UPGRADE PLUGIN](#) [DELETE PLUGIN](#)

- **URN**

This plugin enables the assignment of the Uniform Resource Names to the objects (issues, articles, galley and supplementary files) in OJS.

[ENABLE](#) [UPGRADE PLUGIN](#) [DELETE PLUGIN](#)

User home>journal management>system plugins>Public Identifier Plugins> DOI>setting

Journal Content *

Please select the publishing objects that will have Digital Object Identifiers (DOI) assigned:

NOTE: When using the CrossRef DOIs, please select articles. Article is seen as work, i.e. entity of intellectual and artistic content. Thus, article is the publishing object the CrossRef DOI export a registration is based upon.

- Issues
 Articles
 Galleys
 Supplementary Files

DOI Prefix *

The DOI Prefix is assigned by registration agencies (e.g. CrossRef) and is in the format 10.xxxx (10.1234):

DOI Suffix

A DOI suffix can take any form, but must be unique among all publishing objects with the same prefix assigned:

- Use the pattern entered below to generate DOI suffixes. Use %j for journal initials, %v for volume number, %i for the issue number, %Y for the year, %a for the OJS article ID, %g for galley ID, %s for the OJS supplementary file ID, %p for the page number and %x for "Custom Identifier" (must be enabled in Setup 4.3).

 for issues

 for articles

 for galleys

 for supplementary files.

For example, vol%viss%i%pp%p could create a DOI such as 10.1234/vol3iss2pp230

- Use default patterns.
 %j.v%i for issues
 %j.v%i.%a for articles
 %j.v%i.%a.g for galleys
 %j.v%i.%a.s for supplementary files.
- Enter an individual DOI suffix for each published item. You'll find an additional DOI input each item's meta-data page.

If you change your DOI configuration, DOIs that have already been assigned will not be affected. After the DOI configuration is saved, use this button to clear all existing DOIs so that the new setting effect with existing articles.

Setting DOI (ojs V.2)

Home > User > Journal Management > **Import/Export Data**

Import/Export Data

- QuickSubmit Plugin: One-step submission plugin
- METS XML Export Plugin: Export Journals in METS XML
- DuraCloud Import/Export Plugin: Archive and restore issues using an external DuraCloud service for storage
- Public Identifiers XML Plugin: Import and export public identifiers
- CrossRef Export/Registration Plugin: Export or register article metadata in CrossRef format.
- DataCite Export/Registration Plugin: Export or register issue, article, galley and supplementary file metadata in DataCite format.
- Articles & Issues XML Plugin: Import and export articles and issues
- mEDRA Export/Registration Plugin: Export issue, article and galley metadata in Onix for DOI (O4DOI) format and register DOIs with the mEDRA registration agency.
- DOAJ Export Plugin: Export Journal for DOAJ and supply journal information for inclusion
- Users XML Plugin: Import and export users
- PubMed XML Export Plugin: Export article metadata in PubMed XML format for indexing in MEDLINE.
- Erudit Article Export Plugin: Export articles using the English Erudit DTD

[User home](#)>[export/import data](#)>[Crossref export/registration plugin](#)>[settings](#)

Setting DOI (ojs V.2)

CrossRef Export/Registration Plugin

This plugin can be configured to automatically register Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) with CrossRef. You will need a username and password (available from CrossRef) in order to do so. If you do not have your own username and password you can still export into the CrossRef XML format, but you cannot register your DOIs with CrossRef from within OJS.

Export Data

- Manage DOIs

Settings

You can configure the CrossRef export/registration plug-in here.

Setting DOI (ojs V.2)

Settings

This plugin can be configured to automatically register Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) with CrossRef. You will need a username and password (available from CrossRef) in order to do so. If you do not have your own username and password you can still export into the CrossRef XML format, but you cannot register your DOIs with CrossRef from within OJS.

Requirements

All plugin requirements are satisfied.

Settings

The following items are required for a successful CrossRef deposit.

Depositor name *

Depositor email *

This plugin can be configured to automatically register Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) with CrossRef. You will need a username and password (available from CrossRef) in order to do so. If you do not have your own username and password you can still export into the CrossRef XML format, but you cannot register your DOIs with CrossRef from within OJS.

Username

Password

Please note that the password will be saved as plain text, i.e. not encrypted.

Register DOIs automatically

OJS will deposit article DOIs automatically to CrossRef as articles are published. Please note that this may take a short amount of time after publication to process. You can check for all unregistered DOIs in the unregistered articles listing.

* Denotes required field

CrossRef Export/Registration Plugin

This plugin can be configured to automatically register Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) with CrossRef. You will need a username and password (available from CrossRef) in order to do so. If you do not have your own username and password you can still export into the CrossRef XML format, but you cannot register your DOIs with CrossRef from within OJS.

Export Data

- Manage DOIs

Settings

You can configure the CrossRef export/registration plug-in here.

MATRIK : Jurnal Manajemen, Teknik Informatika dan Rekayasa Komputer

[HOME](#) [ABOUT](#) [USER HOME](#) [SEARCH](#) [CURRENT](#) [ARCHIVES](#)

[Home](#) > [User](#) > [Journal Manager](#) > [Import/Export Data](#) > [CrossRef Export/Registration Plugin](#)

CrossRef Export/Registration Plugin

This plugin can be configured to automatically register Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) with CrossRef. You will need a username and password (available from [CrossRef](#)) in order to do so. If you do not have your own username and password you can still export into the CrossRef XML format, but you cannot register your DOIs with CrossRef from within OJS.

Export Data

- [Manage DOIs](#)

Settings

You can [configure the CrossRef export/registration plug-in here](#).

ISSN: 2476-9843

MATRIK : Jurnal Manajemen, Teknik Informatika dan Rekayasa Komputer

HOME ABOUT USER HOME SEARCH CURRENT ARCHIVES

Home > User > Journal Manager > Import/Export Data > CrossRef Export/Registration Plugin > Manage Article DOIs

Manage Article DOIs

Manage Issues

ALL NOT DEPOSITED FAILED SUBMITTED DEPOSITED ACTIVE

ID	ISSUE	TITLE	AUTHORS	DOI	STATUS
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	VOL 1, NO 1 (2018)	OPTIMASI PENENTUAN NILAI PARAMETER HIMPUNAN FUZZY DENGAN...	Muhammad Yunus	10.30812/v1i1.2	Not deposited
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	VOL 1, NO 1 (2018)	EVALUASI PENERAPAN COMPUTER BASED TEST (CBT) SEBAGAL...	Eka Hartati	10.30812/v1i1.3	Not deposited

1 - 2 of 2 items

Register Check status Download XML Mark registered Select All

Registering many objects can take a long time. So please be patient after clicking the "Register" button. You'll be notified when registration is complete.

Deposit status:

- Not deposited: no deposit attempt has been made for this DOI.
- Submitted: this DOI has been submitted for the deposit.
- Deposited: the DOI has been deposited to Crossref, but may not be active yet.
- Active: the DOI has been deposited, and is resolving correctly.
- Failed: the DOI deposit has failed.
- Marked registered: the DOI was manually marked as registered.

Only the status of the last deposit attempt is displayed.

If a deposit has failed, please solve the problem and try to register the DOI again.

ISSN: 2476-9843

Ciri DOI Aktif

- Cara mengetahui sebuah DOI aktif atau tidak adalah dengan menekan URL DOI yang terdapat pada artikel tersebut baik di OJS maupun di dalam artikel (jika ada)

Penyebab DOI Error

1. Salah menyantumkan nama jurnal pada setup 1.
2. Penambahan karakter pada nama jurnal di OJS seperti tanda () : , ;
3. Pengelola jurnal mengubah-ubah *suffix* DOI.
4. Salah menyantumkan *prefix* DOI penerbitnya.
5. Pengelola jurnal menekan tombol *reassign doi*.
6. Halaman artikel tidak jelas.
7. Nama penerbit berubah-ubah dan tidak dilaporkan ke ISSN BRIN dan Crossref.
8. Lupa Centang pilihan DOI pada setup 4.

Ciri DOI Aktif

- Cara mengetahui sebuah DOI aktif atau tidak adalah dengan menekan URL DOI yang terdapat pada artikel tersebut baik di OJS maupun di dalam artikel (jika ada)

Setting DOI OJS 3

JOURNAL OF NURSING INVENTION
e-ISSN : 2828-481X DOI : <https://doi.org/10.33859/jni>
website: <https://ejournal.unism.ac.id/index.php/jni>

ISSN 772828 481002 Register Login

HOME / Login

Login

Username *

Password *

[Forgot your password?](#)

Keep me logged in

[Register](#)

Accreditation Base on SK NO.177/E/KPT/2024

SINTA 54

..: MENU ..:

- Focus and Scope
- Editorial Board
- Reviewer
- Peer Review Process
- Author Guideline
- Article Processing Charge (APC)

ejournal.unism.ac.id/index.php/JNI/index

Submissions

- My Queue
- Unassigned
- All Active
- Archives

Help

My Assigned

Search Filters New Submission

- Submissions
 - Issues
 - Payments
 - Settings**
 - Users & Roles
 - Tools
 - Administration
- Journal
 - Website**
 - Workflow
 - Distribution

262	No editor has been assigned to this submission.	Incomplete	▼
	been assigned to this submission.	Incomplete	▼
	been assigned to this submission.	Incomplete	▼
324	No editor has been assigned to this submission.	Incomplete	▼
350	No editor has been assigned to this submission.	Incomplete	▼
351	No editor has been assigned to this submission.	Incomplete	▼

A screenshot of a web browser showing the 'Website Settings' page. The browser's address bar shows the URL 'jurnal.universitasbumigora.ac.id/index.php/matrik/management/settings/website'. The page header includes 'MATRIK : Jurnal Manajemen, Teknik Informatika dan ...' and 'Tasks 13'. The 'Plugins' tab is highlighted with a red circle. The main content area shows a table of installed plugins under the heading 'Metadata Plugins (4)'.

Website Settings

Appearance Information Archiving **Plugins** Announcements Navigation Menus Static Pages Help

Installed Plugins Plugin Gallery

Plugins [Search](#) [Upload A New Plugin](#)

Name	Description	Enabled
Metadata Plugins (4)		
▶ OpenURL 1.0 meta-data	Contributes OpenURL 1.0 schemas and application adapters.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
▶ Dublin Core 1.1 meta-data	Contributes Dublin Core version 1.1 schemas and application adapters.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
▶ NLM 3.0 meta-data	Contributes NLM 3.0 schemas and application adapters.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
▶ MODS 3.4 meta-data	Contributes MODS 3.4 schemas and application adapters.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

jurnal.universitasbumigora.ac.id/index.php/matrik/management/settings/website-settings-tab/show-tab?tab=plugins

secure | jurnal.universitasbumigora.ac.id/index.php/matrik/management/settings/website

en, Teknik Informatika dan ... Tasks 13 English View Site admin

service.

Manual Fee Payment The manager will manually record receipt of a user's payment (outside of this software).

Public Identifier Plugins (2)

DOI This plugin enables the assignment of the Digital Object Identifiers to issues, articles and galleys in OJS.

Settings Delete Upgrade

URN This plugin enables the assignment of the Uniform Resource Names to the issues, articles and galleys in OJS.

Report Plugins (5)

Articles Report This plugin implements a CSV report containing a list of articles and their info.

COUNTER Reports The COUNTER plugin allows reporting on journal activity, using the [COUNTER standard](#). These reports alone do not make a journal COUNTER compliant. To offer COUNTER compliance, review the requirements at the Project COUNTER website.

Setelah Pilih Plugin :

- Ceklist DOI
- Pilih Setting

Please configure the DOI plugin to be able to manage and use DOIs in OJS:

Journal Content

Please select the publishing objects that will have Digital Object Identifiers (DOI) assigned:

- Issues
- Articles
- Galleys

DOI Prefix

The DOI Prefix is assigned by registration agencies (e.g. [Crossref](#)) and is in the format 10.xxxx (e.g. 10.1234):

10.30812

DOI Prefix *

DOI Suffix

A DOI suffix can take any form, but must be unique among all publishing objects with the same DOI prefix assigned:

- Use default patterns.

%j.v%vi%i for issues

%j.v%vi%i.%a for articles

%j.v%vi%i.%a.g%g for galleys.

Yang Perlu disetting :

- Pada Journal Content, ceklist Issues dan Articles
- Pada DOI Prefix, isikan dengan Prefix DOI yang didapatkan dari RJI ketika mendaftar DOI
- Pada DOI Suffix, pilih yang "Use default patterns"
- SAVE

MEMASUKKAN DOI ARTIKEL

Submissions x +

Not secure | jurnal.universitasbumigora.ac.id/index.php/humanitatis/submissions

Humanitatis : Journal of Language and Literature Tasks 13 English View Site admin

Submissions

My Queue Unassigned All Active Archives Help

Submissions

Issues

Settings

Users & Roles

Tools

Administration

Future Issues

Back Issues

Search Filters New Submission

0 submissions

Platform & workflow by OJS / PKP

MEMASUKKAN DOI ARTIKEL

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL `jurnaluniversitasbumigora.ac.id/index.php/matrik/managelssues#backIssues`. The page title is "Matrik: Jurnal Manajemen, Teknik Informatika dan ...". The interface includes a sidebar with navigation options: Submissions, Issues, Payments, Settings, Users & Roles, Tools, and Administration. The main content area is titled "Issues" and has two tabs: "Future Issues" and "Back Issues". A "Help" button is visible in the top right of the main area. The "Back Issues" section contains a table with the following data:

Issue	Published	Items	Order
Vol.18 No.1.(2018)	2018-11-30	17	
Edit View Unpublish Issue Delete			
Vol.17 No.2.(2018)	2018-05-31	8	
Vol.17 No.1.(2017)	2017-11-28	10	
Vol.16 No.2.(2017)	2017-05-22	10	
Vol.16 No.1.(2016)	2016-11-29	11	
Vol.15 No.2.(2016)	2016-05-24	8	
Vol.15 No.1.(2015)	2015-11-25	9	

The "Edit" link for the first issue is circled in red. The footer of the browser shows the URL `jurnaluniversitasbumigora.ac.id/index.php/matrik/SS$call$$$/grid/issues/back-issue-grid/edit-issue?issueId=15`.

MEMASUKKAN DOI ARTIKEL

Issue Management: Vol 18 No 1 (2018)

Table of Contents

Issue Data

Issue Galleys

Identifiers

Help

Order

Articles

- ▼ Analisa Penerapan Private Cloud Computing Berbasis Proxmox Virtual Environment Sebagai Media Pembelajaran Praktikum Manajemen Jaringan
 - Submission Remove
- ▶ Pengembangan Sistem VOIP Menggunakan Server Issabel Versi 4.0 dan Tunnel EOIP pada OMNI Hospital Alam Sutera
- ▶ Optimasi Penentuan Nilai Parameter Himpunan Fuzzy dengan Teknik Tuning System
- ▶ Tata Kelola Sistem Informasi Sanken Menggunakan Framework COBIT 5
- ▶ Rancang Bangun Sistem Informasi Persediaan dan Permintaan Barang Proyek Kelistrikan Berbasis Web (Studi Kasus pada PT. Tea Kirana)
- ▶ Perancangan Spasial Pengembangan Potensi Produk Kerajinan berbasis Pemukiman di Taman Nasional Komodo
- ▶ Evaluasi Penerapan Computer Based Test (CBT) sebagai Upaya Perbaikan Sistem pada Ujian Nasional untuk

Yang Perlu diperhatikan : (sumber -> Busro RJI)

- Pastikan nama penulis pada metadata telah lengkap (first name dan last name dan tidak ada yang tertinggal sebagai penulis)
- Pastikan nama penulis pada metadata (xml) ditulis dengan Title Case dan tanpa gelar (contoh: Muhammad Yunus)
- Pastikan Posisi artikel sudah urut sesuai no halaman
- Pastikan penulisan Judul Artikel menggunakan format Title Case/Sentences Case
- Pastikan full text artikel sudah terunggah (pdf di galley)
- Pastikan tahun Copyright di metadata artikel sesuai dengan tahun terbitan
- Pastikan abstrak sudah terisi dengan benar dan tidak ada revisi. (idealnya suatu abstrak adalah 200-300 kata dalam satu paragraf)
- OPSIONAL : untuk kepentingan penyebaran artikel yang lebih baik, pastikan abstrak pada OJS ditulis dalam bahasa inggris
- Klik "Submission" untuk cek dan update

The screenshot shows a web browser window displaying a journal submission system. The URL is jurnal.universitasbumigora.ac.id/index.php/matrik/workflow/index/329/5. The page title is "Analisa Penerapan Private Cloud Computing Berbasis Proxmox Virtual Environment Sebagai Media Pembelajaran Praktikum Manajemen Jaringan" by I Putu Hariyadi, Akbar Juliansyah. The "Production" tab is active, and the "Metadata" link in the top navigation bar is circled in red. A red box highlights the text "Klik metadata untuk cek dan update sesuai note diatas". In the "Production Ready Files" section, a file named "yunus024, Journal editor, P001. I Putu Hariyadi.docx" is listed. In the "Galley" section, a "PDF" link is circled in red. A red box highlights the text "Pastikan file PDF ada dan benar".

Klik metadata untuk cek dan update sesuai note diatas

Pastikan file PDF ada dan benar

Submission and Publication Metadata

Submission Identifiers

Section *
Articles

Articles must be submitted to one of the journal's sections. *

Prefix **Title ***

Examples: A. The

Subtitle

The optional subtitle will appear after a colon (:), following the main title.

Abstract *

STMIK Bumigora Mataram strives to develop a curriculum that adopts the needs of the industrial world. In the past 2 years, Network Management lecturers have experienced problems related to practicum implementation. During this time the learning process uses virtualization installed on each laboratory computer. However, the system has various weaknesses, especially related to the freedom of access and availability. The implementation of Private Cloud Computing based on Proxmox Virtual Environment (PVE) which in the cluster can be a solution to the problems faced. PVE cluster which is made using four servers and integrated with one storage server can be used as a learning media for network management practicum and support high availability so that live migration can be done. Users can manage Virtual Private Servers using Linux Container (LXC) independently with a login and limited access.

List of Contributors

Name	E-mail	Role	Primary Contact	In Browse Lists
I Putu Hariyadi	putu.hariyadi@stmikbumigora.ac.id	Author	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Akbar Juliensyah	akbar.juliansyah@stmikbumigora.ac.id	Author	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Keywords
 Private Cloud x Proxmox x High Availability x Live Migration x Linux Container x

Supporting Agencies

References

[1] NIST. 2013. NIST Cloud Computing Standards Roadmap. https://www.nist.gov/sites/default/files/documents/it/cloud/NIST_SP-500-291_Version-2_2013_June18_FINAL.pdf. Diakses pada tanggal 28 April 2018

[2] IDC. 2016. The Salesforce Economy: Enabling 1.9 Million New Jobs and \$389 Billion in New Revenue Over the Next Five Years. <http://www.salesforce.com/assets/pdf/misc/IDC-salesforce-economy-study-2016.pdf>. Diakses pada tanggal 28 April 2018

Submission and Publication Metadata ✕

Submission Identifiers Help

Public URL identifier

DOI

10.30812/humanitatis.v4i2.403

What you see is a preview of the DOI. Select the checkbox and save the form to assign the DOI.

Assign the DOI to this article

Sampai Tahap ini
kita sudah
berhasil setting &
memasukkan DOI
ke artikel, tapi
**BELUM
DIAKTIVASI !!!**

ARTICLES

Analisa Penerapan Private Cloud Computing Berbasis Proxmox Virtual Environment Sebagai Media Pembelajaran Praktikum Manajemen Jaringan

I Putu Hariyadi, Akbar Juliansyah

Abstract Viewed : 113 | PDF Download : 0 | DOI <https://doi.org/10.30812/matrik.v18i1.329>

1-12

Pengembangan Sistem VOIP Menggunakan Server Issabel Versi 4.0 dan Tunnel EOIP pada OMNI Hospital Alam Sutera

Elly Mufida, David Wardana Agus Rahayu

Abstract Viewed : 78 | PDF Download : 0 | DOI <https://doi.org/10.30812/matrik.v18i1.330>

13-20

Optimasi Penentuan Nilai Parameter Himpunan Fuzzy dengan Teknik Tuning System

Muhammad Yunus

21-28

Crossref

Similarity Check

Powered by iThenticate

MENDELEY

Preserved By :

ADA 3 METODE :

1. MELALUI EXPORT & UPLOAD XML
2. LANGSUNG DI OJS (REGISTER VIA OJS)
3. WEBDEPOSIT (BIASANYA UNTUK JURNAL)

AKTIVASI DOI -> EXPORT XML

A screenshot of a web browser showing the 'Submissions' page of the Matrik journal management system. The browser address bar shows 'jurnal.universitasbumigora.ac.id/index.php/matrik/submissions'. The page has a dark blue sidebar with navigation options: Submissions, Issues, Payments, Settings, Users & Roles, Tools, and Administration. The 'Tools' menu is highlighted with a red dashed box, and a sub-menu is open showing 'Import/Export' and 'Statistics'. The main content area is titled 'Submissions' and has tabs for 'My Queue', 'Unassigned', 'All Active', and 'Archives'. Below this is a section for 'My Assigned' submissions, which includes a search bar, 'Filters', and 'New Submission' button. A table lists several submissions, each with a status of 'Incomplete' and a message: 'No editor has been assigned to this submission.' The table has columns for submission ID, status, and a dropdown arrow. At the bottom of the page, there is a download bar showing a file named 'counter-4.1-AR1-2...xml'.

A screenshot of a web browser displaying the 'Tools' management page for the Matrik journal. The browser address bar shows the URL 'jurnal.universitasbumigora.ac.id/index.php/matrik/management/tools#importexport'. The page has a dark blue sidebar with navigation links: Submissions, Issues, Payments, Settings, Users & Roles, Tools, and Administration. The main content area is titled 'Tools' and has two tabs: 'Import/Export' (active) and 'Statistics'. A 'Help' button is visible in the top right of the content area. A list of plugins is displayed, with the 'CrossRef XML Export Plugin' entry highlighted by a red dashed box. Below the list, the text 'Klik bagian ini' is written.

Tools

Import/Export Statistics Help

- [DataCite Export/Registration Plugin](#): Export or register issue, article, galley and supplementary file metadata in DataCite format.
- [Native XML Plugin](#): Import and export articles and issues in OJS's native XML format.
- [QuickSubmit Plugin](#): One-step submission plugin
- [DOAJ Export Plugin](#): Export Journal for DOAJ.
- [Users XML Plugin](#): Import and export users
- [mEDRA Export/Registration Plugin](#): Export issue, article and galley metadata in Onix for DOI (O4DOI) format and register DOIs with the mEDRA registration agency.
- [PubMed XML Export Plugin](#): Export article metadata in PubMed XML format for indexing in MEDLINE.
- [CrossRef XML Export Plugin](#): Export article metadata in CrossRef XML format.

Klik bagian ini

jurnal.universitasbumigora.ac.id/index.php/matrik/management/importexport

The screenshot shows a web browser window with two tabs: 'CrossRef XML Export Plugin' and 'MATRIK : Jurnal Manajemen, Tek...'. The address bar shows the URL 'jurnal.universitاسbumigora.ac.id/index.php/matrik/management/importexport/plugin/CrossRefExportPlugin'. The page title is 'CrossRef XML Export Plugin'. On the left is a dark blue sidebar with a menu: 'Submissions', 'Issues', 'Payments', 'Settings', 'Users & Roles', 'Tools', and 'Administration'. The main content area has two tabs: 'Settings' (highlighted with a red dashed box) and 'Articles'. Below the tabs is a link for 'DOI Plugin Settings'. A red dashed box highlights a section with the text 'The following items are required for a successful CrossRef deposit.' followed by two input fields: 'Depositor name *' containing 'Muhammad Yunus' and 'Depositor email *' containing 'muhyunus.446@gmail.com'. Another red dashed box highlights a section with instructions on using the plugin to register DOIs directly with CrossRef, including fields for 'Username' and 'Password'. At the bottom, there are two checkboxes for automatic deposit and API testing, and a 'Save' button circled in red. A 'Cancel' button is also visible.

CrossRef XML Export Plugin

Settings Articles **Klik tab Settings**

[DOI Plugin Settings](#)

The following items are required for a successful CrossRef deposit.

Muhammad Yunus
Depositor name *

muhyunus.446@gmail.com
Depositor email *

If you would like to use this plugin to register Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) directly with CrossRef you will need a username and password (available from [CrossRef](#)) in order to do so. If you do not have your own username and password you can still export into the CrossRef XML format, but you cannot register your DOIs with CrossRef from within OJS.

Username

Password

Please note that the password will be saved as plain text, i.e. not encrypted.

OJS will deposit assigned DOIs automatically to CrossRef. Please note that this may take a short amount of time after publication to process. You can check for all unregistered DOIs.

Use the CrossRef test API (testing environment) for the DOI deposit. Please do not forget to remove this option for the production.

Save Cancel **Jika sudah, SAVE dan klik tab Articles**

Bagian ini isi dengan nama dan email yang akan melakukan deposit

Bagian ini kosongkan saja, diisi jika mau deposit otomatis dari OJS

A screenshot of a web browser showing the 'CrossRef XML Export Plugin' interface. The browser address bar shows the URL 'jurnal.universitasbumigora.ac.id/index.php/matrik/management/importexport/plugin/CrossRefExportPlugin'. The page has a dark blue sidebar with navigation options: Submissions, Issues, Payments, Settings, Users & Roles, Tools, and Administration. The main content area is titled 'CrossRef XML Export Plugin' and has two tabs: 'Settings' and 'Articles'. The 'Articles' tab is active and highlighted with a red dashed box. Below the tabs is a table of articles, also highlighted with a red dashed box. The table has columns for 'Select', 'ID', 'Author: Title', 'Issue', 'DOI', and 'Status'. All 'Select' checkboxes are checked. The 'Status' for all articles is 'Not Deposited'.

Select	ID	Author: Title	Issue	DOI	Status
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	333	Merawati et al.; Penerapan SMS Gateway pada Aplikasi Pendaftaran Siswa Baru di SMAN 1 Tanjung	Vol 18 No 1 (2018)	10.30812/matrik.v18i1.333	Not Deposited
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	328	Anggrawan et al.; Tinjauan Kritis Jurnal Ilmiah: Pengembangan dan Evaluasi Formatif Studi Kasus Multimedia untuk Siswa Desain dan Teknologi Pembelajaran	Vol 18 No 1 (2018)	10.30812/matrik.v18i1.328	Not Deposited
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	338	Satria et al.; Tinjauan Kritis Jurnal Ilmiah: "The Influence of Transformational Leadership and Organizational Culture on Learning Organization: a Comparative Analysis of The it Sector"	Vol 18 No 1 (2018)	10.30812/matrik.v18i1.338	Not Deposited
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	325	Budiarjo et al.; Deteksi Citra Kendaraan Berbasis Web Menggunakan Javascript Framework Library	Vol 18 No 1 (2018)	10.30812/matrik.v18i1.325	Not Deposited
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	344	Rizal et al.; Multi Time Steps Prediction dengan Recurrent Neural Network Long Short Term Memory	Vol 18 No 1 (2018)	10.30812/matrik.v18i1.344	Not Deposited
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	347	Ismariaty et al.; Model Pendekatan UTAUT2 Modifikasi pada Analisis Penerimaan dan Penggunaan Teknologi E-Government di Nusa Tenggara Barat	Vol 18 No 1 (2018)	10.30812/matrik.v18i1.347	Not Deposited
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	342	Ayu Dasriani et al.; Architecture Enterprise Program Studi S1 Teknik Informatika dengan TOGAF Architecture Development Method (Studi Kasus : STMIK Bumigora Mataram)	Vol 18 No 1 (2018)	10.30812/matrik.v18i1.342	Not Deposited
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	322	Hutasuhut et al.; Sistem Informasi Pemasaran Paket Tour Koperasi Karya Wisata Senggigi Berbasis Web	Vol 18 No 1 (2018)	10.30812/matrik.v18i1.322	Not Deposited

CrossRef XML Export Plugin x MATRIK : Jurnal Manajemen, Tekn... x +

Not secure | jurnal.universitاسbumigora.ac.id/index.php/matrik/management/importexport/plugin/CrossRefExportPlugin

MATRIK : Jurnal Manajemen, Teknik Informatika dan ... Tasks 13 English View Site admin

CrossRef XML Export Plugin

Settings Articles

Articles **Ceklist artikel yang akan diaktifkan DOI-nya** Search

Select	ID	Author, Title	Issue	DOI	Status
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	333	Merawati et al.; Penerapan SMS Gateway pada Aplikasi Pendaftaran Siswa Baru di SMAN 1 Tanjung	Vol 18 No 1 (2018)	10.30812/matrik.v18i1.333	Not Deposited
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	328	Anggrawan et al.; Tinjauan Kritis Jurnal Ilmiah: Pengembangan dan Evaluasi Formatif Studi Kasus Multimedia untuk Siswa Desain dan Teknologi Pembelajaran	Vol 18 No 1 (2018)	10.30812/matrik.v18i1.328	Not Deposited
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	338	Satria et al.; Tinjauan Kritis Jurnal Ilmiah: "The Influence of Transformational Leadership and Organizational Culture on Learning Organization: a Comparative Analysis of The It Sector"	Vol 18 No 1 (2018)	10.30812/matrik.v18i1.338	Not Deposited
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	325	Budiarto et al.; Deteksi Citra Kendaraan Berbasis Web Menggunakan Javascript Framework Library	Vol 18 No 1 (2018)	10.30812/matrik.v18i1.325	Not Deposited
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AKTIVASI DOI -> EXPORT XML

CrossRef XML Export Plugin x MATRIK : Jurnal Manajemen, Tekn ...

Not secure | jurnal.universitasbumigora.ac.id/index.php/matrik/management/importexport/plugin/CrossRefExportPlugin

MATRIK : Jurnal Manajemen, Teknik Informatika dan ... Tasks 13 English View Site admin

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	30	Sriwinarti et al.: SISTEM INFORMASI DISTRIBUSI PUPUK BERSUBSIDSI PADA KECAMATAN GERUNG LOMBOK BARAT	Vol 15 No 1 (2015)	10.30812/matrik.v15i1.30	Not Deposited
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	29	Yunus: PENERAPAN FUZZY EXPERT SYSTEM UNTUK DIAGNOSA PENYAKIT TELINGA, HIDUNG DAN TENGGOROKAN (THT)	Vol 15 No 1 (2015)	10.30812/matrik.v15i1.29	Not Deposited
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	28	Triwijoyo: SEGMENTASI CITRA PEMBULUH DARAH RETINA MENGGUNAKAN METODE DETEKSI GARIS MULTI SKALA	Vol 15 No 1 (2015)	10.30812/matrik.v15i1.28	Not Deposited
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	27	Adj: ANALISIS PROXIMITY MENENTUKAN LOKASI PERKEBUNAN DI LOMBOK BARAT	Vol 15 No 1 (2015)	10.30812/matrik.v15i1.27	Not Deposited
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	26	Azhar: ANALISA PERBANDINGAN PENERAPAN PBR DAN NON PBR PADA PROTOCOL OSPF UNTUK KONEKSI INTERNET	Vol 15 No 1 (2015)	10.30812/matrik.v15i1.26	Not Deposited
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	25	Abror et al.: MEDIA BANTU PEMBELAJARAN IPA SMP SEBAGAI BEKAL MENGHADAPI UJIAN NASIONAL (UN)	Vol 15 No 1 (2015)	10.30812/matrik.v15i1.25	Not Deposited
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	24	Hasanah et al.: PEMODELAN SISTEM PENJADWALAN PRAKTIKUM LABORATORIUM MENGGUNAKAN ALJABAR MAXPLUS (STUDI KASUS DI STMIK BUMIGORA MATARAM)	Vol 15 No 1 (2015)	10.30812/matrik.v15i1.24	Not Deposited
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	23	Ardhana et al.: OPTIMASI BLOG DENGAN META TAG UNTUK SEO DAN MONITORINGNYA	Vol 15 No 1 (2015)	10.30812/matrik.v15i1.23	Not Deposited

Items per page: NaN

Validate XML before the export and registration.

Download XML Mark active

Pastikan bagian ini TIDAK TERCENTANG, jika sudah "DOWNLOAD XML"

AKTIVASI DOI → EXPORT XML

File Explorer window showing the path: This PC > Data (D:) > Arsip Pribadi > RJI > RJI NTB > Jurnal MATRIK > Issues > Vol 18 No 1 2018 > XML Aktivasi DOI

Name	Date modified	Type	Size
MATRIK Vol 18 No 1 2018	12/1/2018 5:15 PM	XML Document	59 KB

Untuk arsip, ubahlah nama file XML sesuai dengan ISSUES-nya

1 item 1 item selected 58.6 KB

AKTIVASI DOI -> UPLOAD XML

Masuk ke laman : <https://doi.crossref.org/servlet/useragent>

Welcome to Crossref.

- Home
- Users
- Submissions
- Queries
- Reports
- Metadata Admin

No login info in request

Please supply a login and a password:

login:

password:

Masukkan user dan password yang telah diberikan oleh RJI/Crossref

AKTIVASI DOI -> UPLOAD XML

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL <https://doi.crossref.org/servlet/useragent>. The page displays the Crossref logo and a welcome message for 'bumigora'. A navigation menu includes 'Home', 'Users', 'Submissions', 'Queries', 'Reports', and 'Metadata Admin'. The 'Submissions' menu is highlighted with a red box. Below it, a list of options is shown: 'Logout', 'Submission', 'Submission administration', 'Upload submissions', and 'Show my submission queue'. The 'Upload submissions' option is highlighted with a red box. A red arrow points from a text box containing 'Klik salah satu untuk Upload XML' to the 'Upload submissions' option. At the bottom of the page, the copyright notice '© 2000-2019 PILA, Inc.' is visible.

Welcome bumigora

Home Users **Submissions** Queries Reports Metadata Admin

- [Logout](#)

Submission

- [Submission administration](#)
- [Upload submissions](#)
- [Show my submission queue](#)

Klik salah satu untuk Upload XML

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AKTIVASI DOI -> UPLOAD XML

The image shows a browser window with the URL <https://doi.crossref.org/servlet/submissionAdmin?sf=showUpload>. The page is the Crossref submission upload interface. The 'Upload' tab is selected. The 'Type' dropdown is set to 'Metadata'. The 'upload' button is highlighted with a red circle and labeled '1. Pastikan bagian Metadata terpilih'. The 'Choose File' button is highlighted with a red circle and labeled '2. Klik Choose...'. The 'upload' button is also highlighted with a red circle and labeled '5. Klik Upload'. A file explorer window is open, showing the file 'Matrik Vol 18 No 1 2018.xml' selected. The file name is highlighted with a red dashed box and labeled '3. Cari dan pilih file XML'. The 'Open' button is highlighted with a red circle and labeled '4. Klik Open'.

1. Pastikan bagian Metadata terpilih

2. Klik Choose...

3. Cari dan pilih file XML

4. Klik Open

5. Klik Upload

AKTIVASI DOI -> UPLOAD XML

Home Users **Submissions** Queries Reports Metadata Admin

Administration Upload **Show System Queue** System Control Fundref Registry Control Fundref Dedupe Control

SUCCESS

Your batch submission was successfully received.

[Show submission Queue](#)

Success tapi belum tentu aktif !!!

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Note : kita perlu cek lagi untuk memastikan apakah benaran sudah sukses atau tidak

Tools Tambahan dan Link

<https://apps.crossref.org/webDeposit/>

** register DOI Issue dan Jurnal

<https://www.crossref.org/members/prep/>

** Metadata Health Check

<https://doi.crossref.org/servlet/useragent>

** administration control (Upload XML dan Cek Status DOI)

<https://apps.crossref.org/SimpleTextQuery>

** Membantu Memperbaiki metadata reference dan register Metadata Reference ke crossref

Referensi dan Sumber Gambar dalam Presentasi ini diambil dari :

Azhar Aziz Lubis (2022) “ Aktivasi dan *Setting* DOI OJS 2 & 3”

Muhammad Yunus (N.D) “ SETTING & AKTIVASI DOI OJS “

TERIMA KASIH

Any questions?

You can find me at [@relawanjurnal.id](https://www.instagram.com/relawanjurnal.id)